

RAPD (J-06) is faster than RFLP (MGR586) analysis, but it is less informative for phylogenetic analysis because fewer bands are produced for each isolate. Because corresponding groups of isolates are defined with

MGR586 and RAPD (J-06) for the Philippine isolates tested, we propose that the two methods be used together to improve the overall efficiency with which field populations of the pathogen can be analyzed. A preliminary survey using

RAPD can be used to group similar strains and reduce redundancy. All distinct groups can then be sampled adequately for MGR586 analysis to establish the relationships among strains and lineages. ■

Rice dwarf (RD), a new virus disease in the Philippines

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RD is a destructive virus disease that was known to occur only in temperate regions such as Japan, Korea, China, and Nepal.

RD disease symptoms were recently observed in ricefields in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines. Infected plants showed stunting and fine chlorotic specks or streaks on leaf blades (Fig. 1). Most of the plants showing the chlorotic specks were also infected with tungro disease, which obscures the symptoms of RD. However, RD leaf symptoms were clearly visible in plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) only.

Serological tests and electron microscopy confirmed RD infection in plant samples collected from Midsayap. Leaf extracts from symptomatic leaves diluted up to a thousand times gave a strong positive reaction to RD virus

1. RDV-infected leaves showing chlorotic specks or streaks (right); healthy leaf (extreme left).

2. a) RDV particles (arrows); b) RDV and RTBV particles.

(RDV) antiserum in rapid immunofilter paper assay. Electron microscopic observations of clarified infected sap revealed the presence of RDV particles (Fig. 2a), the diameter of which (65 nm)

is about twice that of RTBV (Fig. 2b).

RD was reported in the Philippines in the past, but the case was later proven to be tungro. Hence, this is the first true identification of RD in the Philippines. ■

Integrated pest management—weeds

Weed control in upland ricefields of Karnataka

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Weeds are a big constraint to raising the average upland rice yield in Karnataka from the current low of about 1 t/ha. Hand weeding is very effective but requires a lot of labor, thus making it costly for the upland farmer. Suitable herbicides have not yet been found.

To determine effective and economical weed control practices, we experimented during 1989-91 kharif by combining herbicides or using them with cultural practices. Butachlor and pendimethalin were applied alone or in combination with 2,4-D or hand weeding (Table 1). A weed-free treatment, two hand weeding at 20 and 40 d after rice emergence (DE), and nonweeded treatment were used for comparison. Plots were hand weeded in the weed-free check.

The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design. Soil is silty clay loam with pH 7.0, 0.84% organic C, and

an average 0.6 kg P/ha and 114.1 kg K/ha. Avinash in 1989 and 1990 and IET5656 in 1991 were seeded at 100 kg/ha with a spacing of 20 cm between rows. Fertilizer was applied 100-10.9-20.7 kg NPK/ha.

We took weed samples from a 1-m² quadrat and weighed them at the heading stage of the grassy weeds. We recorded yield and yield components from a 5-m² net plot area. Common weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* spp., *Digitaria* sp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. rotundus*, *C. difformis*, *Cyanotis* spp., *Commelina benghalensis*, *Spilanthes paniculata*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, and *Eclipta prostrata*.